

THE EXPRESSIONS OF FACIAL SOMATISM “HEAD” IN ENGLISH IDIOMS

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Annotation: This study is committed to the importance of a comparative find out about of languages in order to perceive their countrywide and cultural specifics.

Key words: somatism, head, idioms, English, meaning, translation, facial.

English language is the international language of business, politics and culture. It has already emerge as the communicative language for extraordinary countries and nationalities. When we are speaking in a new language, sometimes the different man or woman may no longer understand. The listener might also say: "What?" "Could you repeat it again, please?" or may additionally misunderstand our ideas. Worse yet, the listener may additionally get embarrassed and quit the conversation. Eof these situations is a smash in communication, small or large. It is like a spoil in the glide (or movement) of electrical energy in an electrical circuit. If the drift is stopped at any vicinity in the circuit, the entire system stops. When some thing blocks the glide of ideas, the dialog stops.¹ Some breaks in verbal exchange are brought on via vocabulary or grammar mistakes. Other breaks are triggered by using errors in idiomatic expressions.

It has a brilliant significance to use the idiomatic expressions efficaciously in any language, as the language is an organ representing the idea. So, it will not have any sense if there are wrong desire of words. Spoken language is very rich, flexible, vibrant and soundy. Many phrases and expressions die, relaxation and then they come again again. In every idiom we can simply see the exclusive vocabulary, phrasing and some extraordinary fleshbacks of any state.

¹ Abduraimova Anora Norbo'tayevna "Linguacultural Aspects of Somatisms in English, Russian and Uzbek Languages"

An idiom is a phrase or expression that usually presents a figurative, non-literal meaning attached to the phrase; however some phrases end up figurative idioms while maintaining the literal which means of the phrase. Categorized as formulaic language, an idiom's figurative which means is exclusive from the literal meaning. Idioms show up frequently in all languages; in English alone there are an estimated twenty-five thousand idiomatic expressions.

Somatisms are one of the oldest layers in the vocabulary of various languages, reflect the national and cultural specifics of the people, their customs and traditions, convey their many years of experience and spiritual culture, show the effect so extralinguistic factors in the language, express vital concepts, and as a result, they belong to stable part of many languages. The relevance of the content, nationality, vivid imagery, nationality, simplicity of grammatical design and stylistic diversity also contribute to the popularity of SPU. Also, a characteristic feature of somatic phraseology is the presence in many languages of numerous equivalents, very close to each other in meaning and figurativeness. This feature sharply distinguishes somatic phraseological units from mother thematic groups of phraseological units. The coincidence of the figurativeness of somatic phraseological units in different languages is explained not only by borrowing, but also by general patterns that lead to the emergence of close phraseological units, demonstrating the universal nature of the transfer of somatic lexemes, their functional and semantic dynamics in the composition of phraseological units.²

Somatic phraseological units, like idioms, phraseological units of which one of the components include the names of parts of the body of a person or animals ,constitute one of the vast and productive group in the phraseological units.

One of the somatism is facial somatism. It includes head, mouth ,eye, hear, ear, nose, and face. For example: head over heels; behind the ears; back of his hand; head and shoulders above the others, out of elbows, all in my eyes; head over ears

² Kunitskaya N.V., Melnik V.F., Danilov B.S.Functional-semanticdynamicsofsomaticlexemesaspartofphraseological units // Derivatology and dynamics in Romance and Germanic languages. Chisinau, 1989.

There are different idioms in English . They are given some examples with their meaning. In some cases they can be translated with their words in clear meaning.

For example, Get someone or something out of one's head

Definition: remove someone or something from your thoughts (often used in the negative)

I'm really upset that I can't get her out of my head.

She spent three years getting those experiences out of her head

But in some cases, they can never be translated with words.

For example, Lose Your Head

Meaning: usually used when someone gets very angry over some issue and becomes very annoyed. John was told that he was losing his job even though he had performed very well recently.

He confronted his manager and lost his head completely and called his manager some very bad names.³

Using facial somatism in idioms are given in different meaning. In the following, we can see them.

1. *Go over someone's head*

Definition: not be able to understand something

I'm afraid the joke went over her head.

I'm afraid the situation goes over my head.

2. *Fall head over heels in love*

Definition: fall deeply in love

She fell head over heels in love with Tom.

Have you ever fallen head over heels in love?

3. *Bite someone's head off*

Definition: criticize someone strongly

Tim bit my head off last night at the party.

³ <https://www.englishlessonviaskype.com/more-idioms-associated-with-our-body-parts/>

Don't bit my head off just because I made a mistake.

4. *Able to do something standing on one's head*

Definition: do something very easily and without effort

He's able to count backward standing on his head.

Don't worry about that. I can do it standing on my head.

5. *Beat something into someone's head*

Definition: teach someone something by repeating it over and over again

Sometimes you just need to beat grammar into your head.

My father beat the importance of kindness into my head.⁴

In conclusion, we can see using facial somatism, especially head, is widely used in English language. It has different meanings, and they are used to make a good speech. To understand another language, we should learn all features of learning or target languages.

Used literature:

1. Abduraimova Anora Norbo'tayevna "Linguacultural Aspects of Somatisms in English, Russian and Uzbek Languages"
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4. <https://www.thoughtco.com/idioms-and-expressions-with-head-4091924>

⁴ <https://www.thoughtco.com/idioms-and-expressions-with-head-4091924>